

A SPECIAL RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MATTER, ENERGY, INFORMATION, AND CONSCIOUSNESS

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the advantages of describing the universe, or nature, in terms of information and consciousness. Some problems encountered by theoretical physicists in the quest for the theory of everything stem from the limitations of trying to understand everything in terms of matter and energy only. However, if everything, including matter, energy, life, and mental processes, is described in terms of information and consciousness, much progress can be made in the search for the ultimate theory of the universe. As brilliant and successful as physics and chemistry have been over the last two centuries, it is important that nature is not viewed solely in terms of matter and energy. Two additional components are needed to unlock her secrets. While extensive writing exists that describes the connection between matter and energy and their physical basis, little work has been done to learn the special relationship between matter, energy, information, and consciousness.

KEYWORDS

Consciousness, Digital physics, Electrons, Energy, Information, Matter, Particles, Relationship, String theory, Theory of everything.

1. INTRODUCTION

The view of the overwhelming majority of physicists is that the universe is made of matter, which in turn is composed of atoms, that atoms are made up of particles such as electrons, protons, and neutrons, and that protons and neutrons are made up of quarks. In a nutshell, we learn from physics and chemistry that everything is made up of matter. It is clear that the majority of scientists argue that subatomic particles are the basis of our universe. Furthermore, string theory teaches us that subatomic particles are not point-like objects, as is postulated in the standard model, but rather are tiny strings. These strings vibrate at different frequencies, and each different vibration gives birth to a different particle. String theory is one of the most promising candidates for a theory of everything (ToE). It proposes that subatomic particles are strings so tiny that they appear to us as points.

Be that as it may, in spite of this understanding, a sizable number of researchers, including Seth Lloyd [1], Stephen Wolfram [2], Carlos Gershenson [3], and Michael Egnor [4], propose that information is the most fundamental component of the universe. The view that the universe is comprised of bits is developing within the scientific community. A bit is an acronym for a binary digit and is the smallest unit of data in a computer. A bit has a single binary value: zero or one; or alternatively, qubits of information. A qubit stands for a quantum bit. In quantum computing, this is the basic unit of quantum information and is the quantum version of the classical binary bit that is physically realized with a two-state device, as rightly pointed out by Andrei Khrennikov [5]. In

“The Message of the Quantum, “Austrian physicist Anton Zeilinger [6] writes that quantum mechanics is fundamentally about information.

However, others who work in the field of cybernetics describe systems in terms of matter–energy interactions but have added a new element called information, positing the role that information plays in the universe. In contrast, some of those who work in the field of consciousness, such as David Chalmers [7], believe that it is consciousness, which is embedded or imbued in everything, that is fundamental. His view is clearly in tune with some of the founding fathers of quantum mechanics as well as some leading physicists. Consider, for instance, the following statements:

Max Planck: “I regard consciousness as fundamental. I regard matter as derivative from consciousness” [8].

Von Neumann: “Consciousness, whatever it is, appears to be the only thing in physics that can ultimately cause this collapse or observation” [9].

Freeman Dyson: “At the level of single atoms and electrons, the mind of an observer is involved in the description of events. Our consciousness forces the molecular complexes to make choices between one quantum state and another” [9].

Eugene Wigner: “It is not possible to formulate the laws of quantum mechanics in a consistent way without reference to the consciousness” [9].

Pascual Jordan: “Observations not only disturb what is to be measured, they produce it” [9].

Niels Bohr: “Everything we call real is made of things that cannot be regarded as real. A physicist is just an atom's way of looking at itself” [9].

Wolfgang Pauli: “We do not assume any longer the *detached observer*, but one who by his indeterminable effects creates a new situation, a new state of the observed system” [9].

Max Tegmark: “I believe that consciousness is, essentially, the way information feels when being processed” [10].

Before the atomic view took precedence, most, or perhaps all, ancient civilizations believed that the universe (or matter) was composed of four or five elements: air, water, earth, fire, and aether/space. It is well-documented that matter and energy were previously considered separate and distinct entities until Albert Einstein demonstrated that they were the same thing. Can matter–energy be reduced to information? Can we understand matter, energy, and information in terms of consciousness? What is the special relationship between these concepts?

In 2007, Stuart A. Umpleby [11], in his paper titled “Physical relationships among matter, energy and information,” put forward an attempt to connect these three concepts. This paper attempts to go beyond Umpleby’s work and examine the concepts of mass, energy, and information in a new light to show how they, with the addition of the concept of consciousness, are intrinsically connected at the atomic level. Therefore, this paper uses a computational metaphor to extend the concepts of information and consciousness to describe nature. In addition, it explores the advantages and benefits of describing nature as information, as well as the idea that everything in it, from animate to inanimate, is imbued with consciousness.

It is truly unfortunate that not many leading researchers in theoretical physics have paid much attention to thinking in terms of information and consciousness. This is of great concern and is also surprising, given that some of the pioneers of physics found a central place for consciousness in their theories. The present paper proposes that matter, energy, information, and consciousness have a special relationship and that by incorporating the concepts of information and consciousness, we are likely to further our understanding of matter. Therefore, this paper argues in favor of a special relationship between these four concepts, based on quantum theory.

This paper proposes a scientific basis for the way that information and consciousness are fundamental if we are to understand the universe in a new framework and go beyond the current understanding of matter, energy, time, and space. The motivation for this article is introduced, followed by sections describing the ideas and concepts of matter, energy, and information, and consciousness. Furthermore, the exceptional relationship that connects them is explained. The paper study finishes up with suggestions for additional work. More or less, the point of this paper is to outline the way in which information and consciousness are embedded in matter and can be explained as a physical process.

2. MATTER AND ENERGY

The predominant view of matter is that it is something we can feel through our senses by touch or recognize as a particle. The main property of matter is mass. Alternatively, matter is defined as the physical stuff that makes up the universe: for example, things that can be touched and weighed on a balance or scale. On the other hand, energy is a very complex concept to define. Although there are many definitions, the widely accepted meaning of energy is the capacity to do work. In physics, we learn that matter and energy are the same thing in different forms. Matter can turn into energy and vice-versa. For instance, if matter enters a system, that system has also gained energy. Everything in the universe needs energy. For instance, plants, animals, and human beings all need food. We would not survive at all without food or another source of energy.

In physics, we are taught that energy is a property of matter. Energy can be transferred from one object or system to another and converted from one form to another. However, it cannot be created or destroyed. Most people speaking about energy in everyday conversation refer to it as vitality, strength, power, activity, vigor, etc. However, in a scientific sense, energy refers to the ability to do work. On the other hand, Tom Duncan [12] defines work as the transfer of energy involved in moving an object over a distance by an external force.

The nature of energy remains a mystery. Many writers have pointed this out, including Robert Pepperel [13] and Richard Feynman [14]. It is well-documented that many in the scientific community refer to energy as an abstract property. Nobody has ever seen energy, only its manifestations. No wonder Abbot and Van Ness [15], Rose [16], and Pepperel [17] have gone so far as to argue that “Energy is a mathematical abstraction that has no existence apart from its functional relationship to other variables. “Some instances have been pointed out already, in the highly recommended article by Robert Pepperel entitled: “Consciousness as a Physical Process Caused by the Organization of Energy in the Brain”. It should also be pointed out that there are two main forms of energy: kinetic and potential. Kinetic energy is possessed by objects because of their movement, while an object has potential energy because of their relative position or setup. All other types of energy, such as electric, solar, thermal, chemical, and atomic, are in themselves forms of either kinetic or potential energy.

This constant is the same for matter. Despite advanced research in atomic and particle physics, the nature of matter remains deeply mysterious. Physics does not reveal to us anything about the

inherent nature of matter or subatomic particles. It is silent on this question. For instance, the late theoretical physicist, David Bohm, suggested in 1992 that matter is revealed as an ocean of both energy and light: “Matter, as it were, is condensed or frozen light . . . all matter is a condensation of light into patterns moving back and forth at average speeds which are less than the speed of light . . . It is energy and it is also information – content, form, and structure. It is the potential for everything” [18]-[19].

Bohm’s statement, however, brings us to one fundamental question: what is the nature of matter and what it is made of? The need to answer this question led the author [20] to tackle this head-on. Now, we should ask ourselves what matter is made of. Where is the substance of matter? We are taught to believe that the substance of matter is in the atom. However, we learn from physics that atoms are made up of electrons, protons, and neutrons. Is the substance of matter in electrons or protons? The answer is no, simply because these particles are made of tinier particles called quarks and gluons. Let us then ask, is the substance of matter in the quarks or gluons? We do not think along these lines, just in light of the fact that a quark and an antiquark can annihilate each other to produce photons, which are electromagnetic waves. So, as we can see, the attempt to persuade us that a stone is made of some solid entity is misleading and incorrect, thus calling into question the validity of the standard model of physics.

Furthermore, as it was beautifully put by Stephen Hawking [21] in his book *A Brief History of Time*, quoted and discussed by Galen Strawson [22], we learn that physics is “just a set of rules and equations.” The question is, what “breathes fire into the equations and makes a universe for them to describe?” What is the fundamental stuff of physical reality, the stuff that is structured in the way that physics reveals? The answer, again, is that we do not know, except insofar as this stuff takes the form of conscious experience.

We can say that it is *energy* that breathes fire into the equations, using the word “energy” as Heisenberg does when he says, for example, that “all particles are made of the same substance: energy,” but the fundamental question arises again: “What is the intrinsic nature of this energy-stuff?” And the answer, again, is that we do not know, and physics cannot tell us; that is just not its purview. This point about the limits on what physics can tell us is rock solid, and it arises before we begin to consider any of the deep problems of understanding that arise within physics, such as problems with “dark matter” or “dark energy,” for example, or with reconciling quantum mechanics and general relativity theory [21]-[22].

This statement again generates more questions than answers. Is it telling us something about consciousness? Although the denial of the existence of consciousness is clear in this statement, as the intrinsic nature of physical stuff, consciousness is ubiquitous in nature. Matter is not inanimate, but matter is truly alive. All things are pervaded by life and consciousness.

3. MATTER, ENERGY, AND INFORMATION

Amazing work has been done to establish the relationship between matter, energy, and information by those working in the fields of cybernetics, quantum mechanics, quantum information, quantum computing, etc. One of the main reasons is that information is everywhere in the universe; it is found in physical systems, biological systems, chemical systems, the mental realm, etc. Physicists have come to the realization that all physical systems register information while processing it. It is no wonder, then, that digital physicists have argued that the universe computes. Atoms register bits of information such as temperature, position, speed, and velocity. For instance, when two atoms collide, each registers information that is then transformed and processed. Toffoli and his co-author, Edward Fredkin, [23] have shown in their model that each atomic collision performs the

and, *or*, and *not* operations of Boolean algebra in addition to *copy* operations. Figure 1 shows a hypothetical relationship between matter, energy, and information.

So far, we have discussed and defined the concepts of matter and energy, but we have not yet explained the meaning of information. What do we mean by information? Although information is variously and imprecisely defined, a number of definitions have been proposed.

Most importantly, I might want to call attention to how numerous researchers look at information as a major property of nature: as such, a fundamental building block of reality. However, for the likes of Paul Davies [24], it is the most fundamental property of nature. Claude Shannon [25] explains that in communication theory, information can be treated in the same manner as we deal with a physical quantity such as mass or energy.

Figure 1. The relationship between matter, energy, and information.

On the other hand, Carlos Gershenson [26] defines information as anything that an agent can sense, perceive, or observe. He proceeds to argue that this idea can be applied to everything that encompasses us, including matter and energy, since we can perceive it – in light of the fact that it has a characterized structure – and we are operators. On the other hand, Edwin Parker [27] and Marcia J. Bates [28] argue that information is an intelligible entity of organization of matter and energy. In addition, Marcia J. Bates, in “Fundamental Forms of Information,” has elaborated at length about various forms of information, including natural information, represented information, encoded information, embodied information, etc. For a detailed discussion on the nature of information, its definition, and different types, refer to her article.

Having defined the concept of information, let us explore how information interacts with us and with nature. As has been rightly pointed out, when atoms interact, they perform various operations, share information among themselves, and transmit the outcome of their interaction. With biological systems such as cells, organs, organisms, DNA, etc., genetic information is transmitted across generations. Here, we see clearly how matter, energy, and information are all related. Furthermore, in society at large (culture, customs, behaviors, etc.), information is also shared and transmitted across generations.

In business, matter, energy, and information are all related. For the transformation of raw materials into a finished product (matter), energy is needed to operate machines, and information (computer programs, storage, records, customers' orders, etc.) is also necessary. Furthermore, any information passed into and saved in a computer is generally alluded to as data. However, when information is packaged or used for understanding or doing something, it is known as knowledge.

Next, I would like to discuss the chronological relationship between matter, energy, and information at the atomic level, which is illustrated in Table 1. The connection between energy and information has been described by the Hungarian American physicist, Leo Szilard [29]. In 1929, Szilard demonstrated the relationship between information and energy. In 1932, John von Neumann [30] made the mathematical connection between energy (i.e., thermodynamics) and information. In 1961, Rolf Landauer [31] extended von Neumann's work and showed that the irreversible erasure of a bit of information generated a corresponding amount of physical entropy. In the 1970s and 1980s, Bekenstein's [32]–[34] and Hawking's work on quantum gravity led to the development of what is known as Bekenstein–Hawking radiation, which stresses the link between matter, energy, and information.

Perhaps not as well-known is the work of Hans-Joachim Bremermann [35] [36] in the 1960s, whose enormous contributions were later pointed out by Stuart A. Umpleby. As Umpleby explains [11, 370]:

Bremermann suggested that there is an upper bound on the rate at which symbols may be processed by matter. They may be processed at speeds not exceeding Bremermann's limit of 10^{47} bits/gram/sec. Bremermann's limit is derived from the equations $E = mc^2$ and $E = hf$ when one photon is considered equivalent to one bit.

Since a relationship has been established between matter and information, the contributions of Einstein, Szilard, and Bremermann imply that matter, energy, and information are related at the atomic level.

Table 1. Chronological relationship between matter, energy, and information at the atomic level.

1900	Planck proposes that electromagnetic energy is not emitted over a continuous range but rather in bundles.
1905	Einstein proposes the equivalence of matter and energy.
1929	Szilard proposes a connection between energy and information.
1932	John von Neumann proposes a conceptual link between quantum measurement and thermodynamic entropy.
1948–1949	Shannon conducts landmark work on the relationship between information and thermodynamic entropy.
1961	Landauer takes John von Neumann’s work to new heights by showing that the irreversible erasure of a bit of information de facto generates a corresponding amount of physical entropy.
1962–1965	Bremermann’s limit states a relationship between matter and information.
1970s–1980s	Work on quantum gravity leads to the development of Bekenstein–Hawking radiation, which stresses the link between matter, energy, and information.
Present	Digital physics (i.e., the physics of information and computation) implies that matter, energy, and information are all related at the atomic level.

4. CONSCIOUSNESS: BEYOND MATTER, ENERGY, AND INFORMATION

Science is an evolving subject, a dynamic process, in that we continuously discover, add to, and modify our body of scientific knowledge as new evidence emerges. It is possible that many discoveries, laws of the universe, and even different types of particles are yet to be found. It is unfortunate that many scientists take for granted that everything from biology, chemistry, physics, psychology, mental processes, etc. can be explained by the four fundamental concepts: matter, energy, space, and time. This prevailing attitude suggests that we may be missing some pieces to unlock the puzzle of the ToE. In a nutshell, many scientists stress the idea that, in theory, we could account for all the complex processes occurring in the universe in terms of matter composition, energy, forces, and work, meaning we could understand everything as physical, chemical, or biological processes.

It is the author’s intention to show that consciousness and information, along with matter and energy, are fundamental principles of nature. He supports the vision of the philosopher David Chalmers [37], who urges researchers to truly think about panpsychism, which is the possibility that consciousness, however, elementary, pervades everything in the universe. Along the same line of reasoning, Galen Strawson [22] finds the idea, used in everyday language or books by scientists, that we do not know what consciousness is, appalling. He goes on to argue that [I] found the issues surrounding consciousness odd in light of the fact that we know precisely what conscientiousness is—where by consciousness I mean what the vast majority mean in this discussion: experience of any sort whatever. It is the most recognizable thing there is, regardless of whether it is understanding of feeling, torment, understanding what somebody is stating, seeing, hearing, contacting, tasting, or feeling. It is in certainty the main thing known to man whose extreme inborn nature we can profess to know. It is absolutely unmysterious.

For several years now, the view that consciousness emerges or is derived entirely from physical matter has slowly been losing ground, as it is unable to explain how consciousness arises from

matter. Then again, the possibility that consciousness is a different element that is distinct from physical matter is gaining ground. The faculties of mind, intellect, and personality are simply manifestations of consciousness. The nonmaterial part of us is consciousness, soul, or spirit, and the body is simply the means through which consciousness expresses itself and experiences the world. Spirit, consciousness, inner self, anima/animus, life energy, essence, or 'I' are essentially synonyms for the word 'soul.' Consciousness operates throughout the body. Apparently, it is not the physical body that is liable for our actions but the consciousness or thinking being that forms the operating system of the body.

Very simply it is I, the self, or the soul. Consciousness utilizes the word 'I' for itself and the word 'my' when alluding to the body: my hand, my mouth, my cerebrum, etc. I am not the same as my body. The idea that the entire universe is conscious, or alternatively, that consciousness pervades everything in the universe, is gaining ground. There is no doubt that the physical universe together with the laws and properties of matter, energy, etc. are the physical manifestations of consciousness. The soul or consciousness in many entities is in a latent state. Consciousness also serves as an organizing principle, integrating everything in the physical body and giving coherency and stability of identity.

Minerals, plants, animals, and human beings are the physical expressions of consciousness. Consciousness expresses itself in ascending levels; that is, the consciousness of a mineral is more latent than that of a human being. To evolve from a lower to a higher dimension, consciousness needs a physical form, a body through which it can express itself. Minerals, plants, animals, and humans all have an awareness appropriate to their own level of consciousness, and each type of entity has a kind of awareness that is different from the others. This means that each type has its own form of perception and uses its consciousness according to its level of development.

For instance, in "Plants do sums to get through the night," Martin Howard [38] shows that plants can compute and carry out complex arithmetic calculations to guarantee that they have enough food to last for the duration of the night. This example shows that one does not need a brain to process information. Everything in the universe processes information, and every cell is independently imbued with consciousness. The most radical shift in the history of science is taking place. It appears that the materialistic and reductionist worldview is slowly being replaced. Consciousness is the pattern of organization of matter, energy, and information.

Many physicists have avoided dealing with the concept of consciousness. This may date back to the unwillingness of Sir Isaac Newton to indicate the primary source of gravity. "Hypothesis non fingo," he replied, which translates as, "I do not have a clue." What is concealed in matter is the expression of consciousness, which is primary. Therefore, it is important to remind our readers that the physics of Sir Newton was constructed without solving two fundamental problems: the causes of attraction and the workings of consciousness. Physics and chemistry tell us little or nothing about the intrinsic nature of matter, they only describe for us what matter does. In any case, we think there must be more to the idea of matter and physical elements.

However, several scientists have put forward suggestions about how quantum theory might explain consciousness. One example can be found in the works of Stuart Hameroff and Roger Penrose [39]. In addition, Carlos Eduardo Maldonado [40] argues that consciousness processes information, and it processes information in non-algorithmic ways, suggesting the physical existence of something with important properties. Furthermore, Inomata Shuji, a Japanese researcher, has proposed a formula of interchange of consciousness, matter, and energy.

Shuji pointed out that the existence of this relation (formula) was predicted well before him by the English astronomer V.A. Firsoft. According to Shuji, Firsoft stated that “Mind [consciousness] is a universal entity or interaction of the same level as electricity or gravity and we can expect a formula similar to Einstein’s famous $E = mc^2$ to exist for it.” Shuji has obtained the formula, the steps for which are reproduced in [41].

Following the development of atomic physics, we have learned that atoms are made up of various small particles, i.e., a nucleus with electrons around it. We currently realize most of the atom is empty space; is vacant space; there are not in reality any particles there but rather essentially the probabilities of observation. In fact, there are no particles, and the electron is simply an idea or model that we have developed to describe what we are observing. Hans Peter Dürr, the German theoretical physicist, quoted here from Peter Russel [42], sums it up in the following terms: “Whatever matter is, it is not made of matter.”

Figure 2. The double-slit experiment. Photons or particles of matter produce a wave pattern when two slits are used.

One of the most important fundamental properties of consciousness found in quantum systems is the capacity to choose or decide. This can be illustrated by a double-slit experiment, figure 2. This is one of the most well-known experiments in physics. The quantum double-slit experiment shows how our consciousness and the physical world are entwined, making us to understand that the observer creates reality. The result of the test shows that light and matter can show the attributes of both classically defined waves and particles, while also displaying the fundamentally probabilistic nature of quantum mechanical phenomena. The quantum double-slit experiment has played a key role in understanding how consciousness shapes the nature of our physical world or reality. Despite the fact that mainstream researchers have not yet thought of solid clarifications for the extent of this connection, the appropriate response is that consciousness is fundamental, the source of everything, and that electrons are embedded with consciousness.

Electrons possess this ability to decide, although they lack the ability to communicate their experience in the way that humans do. “Choosing” is one of the fundamental properties of consciousness. Fundamental particles have life and experience, and consciousness is telling us something about the intrinsic nature of these subatomic entities. Quantum systems display what I can only term consciousness. Here, I emphasize the fact that subatomic particles “choose,” which suggests the presence of consciousness, as expressed by the ability to choose. This leads to the

conclusion that physics, or alternatively, quantum mechanics, is a theory of information and consciousness. This article is based on the thesis that consciousness is more fundamental than matter, energy, and information in the fabric of reality and the quest to understand the universe. I have demonstrated how these four building blocks are interconnected and the special relationship that exists between them.

5. CONCLUSION

This paper puts forward ideas on information and consciousness that require further development, analysis, review, and extension in various fields. Describing the universe in terms of the four concepts constitutes an alternative option worth exploring to unlock the missing puzzle pieces in the quest for the ToE. It is important that the ideas presented here are explored and elaborated further. One important aspect, which is key to unlocking the ToE, is the understanding of information encoded in the universe and the role that consciousness plays in the running of the human, animal, vegetable, and mineral kingdoms.

It is now becoming clear that matter, energy, information, and consciousness are deeply interrelated and all part of the same web. One cannot exist without the others. There is no doubt that the implications of an informational and consciousness model of physics, chemistry, and biology ought to be addressed because most researchers have only focused on understanding the universe in terms of matter and energy. It appears that if consciousness is a natural physical process that is behind matter, energy, and information, and organizes them in the physical universe, then the implications for humanity are profound. To emphasize the role of consciousness in the physical universe, Maldonado points out that “The observation is conscious, and consciousness transform data into information, and information into knowledge.”

It appears that information and consciousness are not emergent phenomena but are ever-present in the universe and in physics, chemistry, and biology. Consciousness is a physical property of the universe. This paper shows the relationship between matter, energy, information, and consciousness, on the premise of the existence of consciousness, which is imbued in everything in the universe. The author posited the existence of information and consciousness, which is the starting point for this paper, and the need for it was clearly established.

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Author Short Biograph

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